

장소: 시곡암

Place: Simgogam (Simgok Hermitage)

주소: 서울특별시, 성북구, 정릉 3 동

Address: Jeongneung 3(sam)-dong, Seongbuk District, Seoul, South Korea

심곡암 주지 원경스님과 인터뷰 (13.10.2024)

Interview with Venerable Wongyeong, the abbot of Simgok Hermitage (13.10.2024)¹

도미닉 루타나: 동물천도재를 도입한 이유와 계기에 대해서 설명해 주세요.

원경스님: 요즘 반려동물과 함께 살아가는 사람들이 많습니다. 시대의 흐름에 맞게 가족으로 받아들이는 동물들도 많아서 참여하게 되었어요. 그리고 떠난 동물들도 중요하지만 남아있는 사람들의 마음을 위해 그런 의례가 필요합니다.

Dominik Rutana: Please explain the circumstances and rationale behind the establishment of *dongmul chondojae* (rituals for sending the souls of animals to the afterlife)?

Venerable Wongyeong: It's becoming more and more common for people to live with their pets, and there are lots of animals that are accepted as family members, which is why I got involved. While it's important to honour the animals who have passed away, we also need to recognize the feelings and needs of those who remain.

도미닉 루타나: 의례 형식에 대해서 설명해주세요.

원경스님: 천도재 형식과 같고, 제가 직접 동물천도제 발원문도 썼어요.

Dominik Rutana: Could you please provide a description of the format of the ritual?

Venerable Wongyeong: It is similar to the *cheondojae* (for people); however, I have also composed a special ritual prayer text for the *dongmul chondojae*.

¹ Interview and English Translation from Korean by Dominik Rutana. Contact. drutana@swps.edu.pl.

도미닉 루타나: 일년에 천도재를 몇 번이나 지내시는지, 반려동물 외에 다른 동물을 위한 천도재를 지내고 싶은 사람들도 찾아오시는지를 궁금합니다.

원경스님: 합동천도재도 지냈고 개별 천도재도 지내요. (불교) 신자가 아닌 사람들도 찾아와서 요청하면 지냅니다. 처음 지낸 이유는 신도회장이 예전에 „사냥꾼”이었어요. 살생을 많이 했던 직업이라 그 분으로 인해 시작되었어요.

Dominik Rutana: I was wondering how often you perform the ritual on an annual basis. I would also like to know if there are people who want to hold the *chondojae* for animals other than their pets.

Venerable Wonyeong: I've done combined *chondojae* for all the animals that have died, as well as rituals for individuals. If any non-Buddhist believers find me and ask me to perform a ritual for them, I'd be happy to do that. I decided to perform the ritual for the first time because the leader of our believers' association used to be a hunter, which is a profession that involves a lot of killing.

도미닉 루타나: 동물천도재 미래에 대해서 어떻게 생각하세요?

원경스님: 천도재는 앞으로도 진행할 생각이고, 여건과 그 때의 상황들에 따라 정확히 알 수 있어요. 매년 정해진 날짜가 없어요.

Dominik Rutana: What do you think about the future of *dongmul chondojae*?

Venerable Wonyeong: We will continue to perform the ritual, although we don't have a fixed date for it. It will all depend on the conditions and the circumstances at the time.